

Original Research

Effect of Social Selling on Salespersons' Performance: Evidence from B2B Salespersons in an Emerging Country Context

Vivian Obianuju Dike^{ID}, Nwaizugbo Ireneus Chukwudi^{ID}

Obinna Christian Ojiaku^{1 ID}

Department of Marketing, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

Received 4 March 2024 Revised 22 May 2024 Accepted 28 May 2024

Abstract

The rise in the use of social media for businesses and sales has made it a valuable tool for customer acquisition, retention, and relationship management. However, the diversity it is used and extent to which its function improves performance remains underexplored in the literature. This study examines the effect of social selling on salespersons' performance. Specifically, the study examines the effects of social media insights, connections, and engagement on sales performance. Data was collected from B2B salespeople in Anambra using a purposive and snowballing technique to collect data both online and offline. A structured questionnaire consisting of 5-items Likert scales questions adapted from the literature was used for data collection. The scales were validated using senior academics from a federal university in Southeast, Nigeria while Cronbach alpha was used to test reliability of the. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested based on dimensions of social selling using multiple regression analysis via SPSS version 22. The result showed that social selling insight and social selling engagement have a positive and significant effect on sales performance. While the effect of social selling connections was not significant. It was therefore recommended that firms should train salespeople on how to use various social media platforms and understand the nuances of social media use. It is also important that salespeople are equipped and encouraged to 'listen' to social conversations for mentions about their brands, industry, or competitors. Sales organization should also monitor conversations for opportunities to engage – that is, by identifying relevant conversation or trending topics.

Keywords: Nigeria, social media connections, social media engagement, social media insights, social selling, sales performance.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: oc.ojiaku@unizik.edu.ng

Introduction

In the modern business environment, the pervasive adoption of social media by consumers has emerged as a crucial asset for businesses. On average, consumers now spend a significant 151 minutes daily on social media platforms, with particularly high usage rates observed among Nigerians (Dixon, 2023). This increased engagement extends to business buyers, where three out of four now rely on social media for their purchasing decisions (Mora Cortez et al., 2023). As a result, social media has captured the attention of sales professionals and business managers alike, leading to a reshaping of the selling ecosystem (Good & Schwepker, 2022; Agnihotri et al., 2012).

This transformation has placed additional demands on salespeople, requiring them to embrace social media as a vital tool for customer acquisition, retention, and relationship management (Franck & Damperat, 2023; Schendzielarz et al., 2022; Terho et al., 2022). This integration of social media into the selling process is commonly referred to as social selling. Aligned with the Ancillai et al. (2019) study, we define social selling as a salesperson selling approach 'which leverages social channels for understanding, connecting with, and engaging influencers, prospects, and existing customers at relevant customer journey touchpoints for building valuable business relationships. Specifically, social selling is a three-dimensional construct with three formative dimensions of i) insight acquisition, ii) connecting, and iii) engagement, which together determine the construct. In other words, although the dimensions may correlate, they do not need to occur simultaneously, as a salesperson can score highly in the intelligence generation dimension but not in engagement. Instead, it is logical to consider that the overall level of social selling is determined by the contributions of its key dimensions (see Jarvis, MacKenzie, & Podsakoff, 2003, p. 203). In the context of this study, social selling is an approach that relies on the extensive use of social networking channels for understating customers, interacting and connecting with them and ultimately building a valuable relationship with them. It involves the use of Whatsapp, LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook to create contents that resonates with customers, connect, and engage with customers.

Social selling is a sophisticated approach that is grounded in the strength of social media alliances within a social enterprise. It emphasizes salespeople's use of social interaction-enhancing platforms for content creation and networking (Ancillai et al., 2019). Sales professionals leverage social selling for researching, prospecting, networking, and building relationships. This involves sharing relevant content and addressing inquiries from both prospects and existing customers (Minsky & Quesenberry, 2016). Essentially, social selling is a digital marketing strategy at the personal selling level. It utilizes content and social media marketing to comprehend, connect with, and engage influencers, prospects, and existing customers at various touchpoints in the customer purchasing journey, fostering valuable business relationships (Ancillai et al., 2019).

Numerous studies have explored the impact of social media on salespersons' functions. For example, Itani et al. (2023) examined social media use by B2B salespeople, focusing on its influence on value co-creation and cross/upselling performance. Cheng et al. (2023) investigated how salespeople emulate influencers to enhance the value creation process.

Zhou and Charoensukmongkol (2023) concentrated on social media's role in B2B export performance, while Chaker et al. (2022) explored the intersection of inside sales and social media use. Ogilvie et al. (2018) delved into the effect of salesperson social media technology use on performance, particularly through behaviors and characteristics.

Despite these valuable insights, researchers like Ancillai et al. (2019) and Terho et al. (2022) call for additional research to better understand how the dimensions of social selling impact sales performance. Moreover, there is a noticeable gap in research on how social media tools assist salespeople in emerging country contexts, particularly in Nigeria. Additionally, a significant portion of the literature on social media use in sales has predominantly adopted the unidimensional construct of social media use. Accordingly, studies investigating how salesperson's use of social media to generate insight, engage, and connect with customers influence their sales performance in B2B sales context is scant. Moreover, evidence from an emerging country context like Nigeria is also lacking. To address these gaps, this study contributes by extending the literature on social media use, specifically in the realm of social selling. It employs multidimensional scales collect data from B2B salespeople and to predict performance. It aims to explore how a salesperson's use of social selling to generate insight, connections, and engagement with their customers intricately influences their selling performance. In particular, this study seeks answers to the research question: what extent does social media insight, connection, and engagement affect salespersons' performance in an emerging country context - Nigeria?

The rationale for studying an emerging country such as Nigeria provides interesting insight towards understanding how salespeople navigate the use of social networking site to meet their selling objectives. The Nigerian selling environment is unique due to its underdeveloped nature compared to advanced countries. However, Salespeople capitalize on social commerce platforms such as Instagram, WhatsApp, and Facebook to expand their sales reach. By utilising these channels effectively, companies can engage with potential customers, showcase their products, and facilitate transactions, all within the digital space (Euromonitor, 2024). Also, despite the use of social selling tools, to an extent, some features and applications on these social selling platforms are seldom not available to salespeople in Nigeria. This provides significant rationale for understanding B2B salespeople perspective from this context.

Review of Related Literature

Social Selling

In the realm of sales, two fundamental concepts—social media use and social selling—play a crucial role in guiding how sales professionals leverage social platforms for selling, each embodying a distinct approach. This section delves into the intricacies of social selling, building upon earlier discussions on social media use.

Social selling, as described by Ancillai et al. (2019), is an approach where salespersons utilize social channels to understand, connect with, and engage influencers, prospects, and existing customers across various touchpoints in the customer journey. This strategic engagement aims to cultivate valuable business relationships by applying digital

marketing principles, including social media and content marketing, to the sales process (Mostafa & Kasamani, 2022).

In simpler terms, social selling is about selling without a traditional sales pitch. Schmitt et al. (2021) characterize it as the complete integration of social media into daily sales activities, facilitating the entire sales process. Trainor (2012) emphasizes its role in a company's ability to navigate the sales cycle through customer knowledge and relationship networks. Vander Schee et al. (2020) highlight social selling as a platform that fosters information exchange between buyers and sellers, contributing to network expansion and supporting the sales process.

Social selling serves as a pivotal tool for prospecting, networking, follow-ups, content sharing, and addressing customer inquiries and reviews (Minsky & Quesenberry, 2016). In essence, "social selling" is instrumental in realizing, building, and supporting relationships between customers and salespeople (Mostafa & Kasamani, 2022). Franck and Damperat (2023) demonstrated the direct impact of social media use on salesperson performance.

Sales performance

Sales performance is multifaceted, encompassing effectiveness, behavior, and interaction. Effectiveness is quantified through metrics like units sold, market share, quota attainment, and customer acquisition (Chawla et al., 2020). Behavior, however, evaluates actions aligned with organizational objectives. Measurement methods vary, including subjective self- or manager-reported behaviors. Alternatively, some views merge effectiveness and behaviors into a unified perspective. For instance, Jridi et al. (2019) advocate for outcome-based performance measures. This approach objectively evaluates a salesperson's results against company objectives, as reported by the salesperson. This study, therefore, underscores the importance of considering both objective outcomes and subjective behaviors in evaluating sales performance, and aligning with a holistic view advocated by contemporary research (Chawla et al., 2020; Jridi et al., 2019).

Theoretical Background and Hypotheses

The Resource-Based View (RBV) theory posits that a company's success hinges on its resources and capabilities, serving as the driving forces behind its performance and long-term prosperity (Chatterjee et al., 2022; Barney, 1991). Resources, which can be tangible or intangible, encompass assets, knowledge, and processes crucial for formulating and implementing strategies. Meanwhile, capabilities involve the strategic development of a diverse set of resources, empowering firms to achieve superior performance (Choudhury & Harrigan, 2014).

RBV asserts that a competitive advantage arises when a firm controls a combination of valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources and capabilities (Eller et al., 2020). Numerous studies consistently affirm the effectiveness of RBV in elucidating the connection between organizational resources and firm performance (Mikalef & Gupta, 2021; Chatterjee et al., 2022). For example, Mikalef and

Gupta (2021) demonstrated how organizational resources fuel the development of AI capabilities, leading to improved performance, thereby highlighting RBV's relevance in understanding the impact of social selling on performance (Pervaje, 2011). In the context of sales organizations, leveraging social media, aligning resources with strategic goals and market opportunities becomes paramount. These resources encompass technologies, data, platforms, and digital capabilities, all contributing to enhanced efficiency, innovation, and enriched customer experiences (Pervaje, 2011). By monitoring and mining customer data, sales teams gain valuable insights into customer behaviors, market trends, and dynamics, ultimately driving informed decision-making and improved sales performance.

Dimensions of Social Selling

Social selling, as conceptualized by Ancillai et al. (2019) and Terho et al. (2022), encompasses three key dimensions: insight acquisition, connecting, and engagement.

Insight acquisition

Insight acquisition is the foundational dimension of social selling, involving the collection of valuable information from social channels about potential and current customers, as well as other relevant individuals. This process, often referred to as 'social listening,' enables sales professionals to understand customer needs and preferences, thereby aiding in effective needs discovery. Moreover, insights gathered from social media platforms empower salespeople with valuable customer data, facilitating the identification of potential leads and the enhancement of customer intelligence. This information is crucial for qualifying prospects, tailoring sales approaches, and preparing for initial contacts (Schendzielarz et al., 2022).

Cheng et al. (2023) highlight that B2B salespeople utilize social media for buyer surveillance, which informs content creation and sales message development. Similarly, Itani et al. (2017) demonstrate the positive impact of social media on sales performance, attributing it to the gathering of competitive intelligence and the encouragement of adaptive selling practices

H₁: The dimension of Insight in Social selling will have a positive effect on salespersons' performance

Connection

The second dimension of social selling, as outlined by Ancillai et al. (2019), revolves around establishing connections with prospects, existing customers, and other relevant individuals during critical touchpoints in the customer journey. This dimension leverages social media's conventional role in facilitating social interactions, enabling salespeople to engage in meaningful dialogues through activities such as chatting, commenting, and responding to queries. Through consistent engagement, sales professionals can cultivate and nurture relationships with customers and other key stakeholders (Terho et al., 2022; Schendzielarz et al., 2022).

This connection is particularly valuable as it allows salespeople to bypass traditional gatekeepers like secretaries and assistants, thereby gaining direct access to prospects (Schmitt et al., 2021). Recent research underscores the importance of social media in enhancing salespeople's social capital, which directly impacts their market knowledge and reputation, and indirectly influences their networking efforts (Itani et al., 2023). Accordingly, we hypothesize as follows:

H₂: The dimension of Customer Connection in Social selling will have a positive effect on salespersons' performance

Engagement

The third dimension of social selling revolves around engaging customers and relevant stakeholders through valuable content (Ancillai et al., 2019). Sales professionals strategically share this content to influence customers, encouraging them to invest time and attention in interactions, thereby laying the groundwork for future relationships. In today's era of well-informed and empowered customers, salespeople must capture attention by providing content that is relevant, timely, and compelling, addressing significant business challenges and driving engagement (Terho et al., 2022a).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Terho et al. (2022) also emphasize the role of social media engagement in building a consistent personal brand or thought leadership, which enhances a salesperson's performance. Furthermore, Mora Cortez et al. (2023) highlight that followers and website visits positively impact sales revenue, with sales posts and website visits contributing to the growth in follower numbers. Social media activity, such as posts and new followers, also positively correlates with engagement. Additionally, Chaker et al. (2022) note that inside salespeople who leverage social media and digital technology resources can engage with customers digitally, thus influencing their job performance. Accordingly, we hypothesize as follows:

H₃: The dimension of Customer Engagement in Social selling will have a positive effect on salespersons' performance

Previous Research

From empirical literature on social selling, Itani et al. (2023) developed a model showing that social media use by B2B salespeople enhances social capital, market knowledge, and reputation, indirectly improving networking. Also, social selling as reported by Franck and Damperat (2023) boosts salesperson performance and indirectly through social proximity and relationship quality. Related to insight generation, Cheng et al. (2023) discovered that B2B salespeople use social media for buyer surveillance, influencing content creation and sales messaging. Zhou and while Mora Cortez et al. (2023) found that LinkedIn engagement boosts sales revenue and follower count in tandem with the social selling engagement framework.

More significantly, Terho et al. (2022) validated measures for social selling, highlighting its significant effects on customer acquisition and performance. And Chaker et al. (2022) demonstrated how social media enables inside salespeople to engage digitally with customers, enhancing job performance. Schendzielarz et al. (2022) showed that social media adoption improves customer acquisition performance when communication is customized.

Another study by Zhou and Charoensukmongkol (2021) showed how social media use enhances customer qualification skills and adaptive selling behaviors, especially for Facebook users proficient in English. While Ancillai et al. (2019) conceptualized social selling, emphasizing its role in building business relationships through digital channels. Ogilvie et al. (2018) observed that social media enhances communication and adaptability behaviors, though not always sales performance. Itani et al. (2017) found that social media improves sales performance by gathering competitive intelligence.

Despite extensive research, gaps remain, especially regarding social media's role in emerging markets and its multidimensional impacts on sales performance. This study seeks to address these gaps by exploring social selling through a multi-dimensional lens.

Methodology

Design and Sample

This study utilized a survey research design focusing on salespeople in the business-to-business (B2B) sector. Employing a cross-sectional survey approach, the research targeted B2B salespeople in Anambra State. The exact population figures within the study's scope remained unknown due to confidentiality concerns related to tax. Despite the potential availability of figures from public sources or company records, they were often inaccessible for tax-related reasons. The sample size, determined using Topman Rank's formula for infinite population, was set at 180. Employing a multi-method approach involving judgmental sampling and an online survey, data collection involved

reaching out to salespeople through WhatsApp and social media direct messages. Additionally, a snowballing technique was employed, where initially sampled salespeople were asked to share the survey link with their colleagues.

Measurement Instrument

The primary data collection tool was a structured questionnaire divided into two sections: Section A focused on demographic questions, and Section B addressed social selling and sales performance measures. Dimensions of social selling were adapted from Terho et al. (2022), while sales performance measures were derived from Good and Schwepker (2022). The questionnaire utilized a Likert scale ranging from 5 to 1, where 5 indicated strong agreement and 1 indicated strong disagreement. The instrument's reliability was tested using Cronbach alpha (benchmark > 0.70; Bainsstein & Nunnally, 1994), while face validation was performed by some senior academics in the faculty of management sciences of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Findings

A total of 180 questionnaires were distributed to salespeople both online and offline, with 162 returned and 18 rejected due to incomplete filling. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics using frequencies and percentages. Principal Component Analysis reduced the data and tested for commonality, while Multiple Regression Analysis examined proposed hypotheses.

Respondents Profile

Table 1 reveals key demographics: 56% of respondents were male, 60% were aged between 26 and 35, and 47% were married. About 90% held at least a bachelor's degree, with 41% having 4 to 6 years of sales experience. Monthly earnings ranged between 150,000 and 250,000 for the majority. Notably, 44% of respondents sold financial services, and the preferred communication platforms were WhatsApp (38%) and Facebook (31%).

Table 1. Respondents Profile

Variable	Responses	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	91	56
	Female	71	44
Age	18-25 yrs.	19	12
	26-35 yrs.	97	60
	36- 45 yrs.	29	18
	46 -55 yrs.	12	7
	Above 55 yrs.	5	3
Marital Status	Single	70	43
	Married	92	47
Educational Qualification	O'level/School certificate	3	2
	OND	13	8
	BSc/HND	86	53

Variable	Responses	Frequency	Percent
	Postgraduate	60	37
Working Experience	< 1 year	11	7
	1 – 3 years	52	32
	4 – 6 years	66	41
	7 - 10 years	23	14
	>10 years	10	6
Income (per month)	< 80,000	20	12
	80,001-150,000	35	22
	150,001-250,000	60	37
	250,001-500,000	32	20
	> 500,000	15	9
Sector	FMCGs	51	31
	Pharmaceuticals	29	18
	Financial Services	71	44
	Electronics	6	4
	Others	5	3
Social media mostly used	Twitter	15	9
	Facebook	50	31
	LinkedIn	21	13
	WhatsApp	62	38
	TikTok	5	3
	Instagram	7	5
	Others	2	1
	Total	162	100

Factor Analysis and Reliability Score

Before conducting hypothesis testing, a factor analysis was performed to streamline the dataset. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed using an Eigenvalue threshold of 1 and the Varimax Rotation Method, excluding values below four. The analysis revealed four distinct factors: the first factor measured sales performance, the second factor involved social selling insights, the third factor focused on social selling connections, and the fourth factor addressed social selling engagement. Together, these factors explained 68.89% of the dataset's total variance. To ensure the reliability of the factors, a test was conducted, surpassing the accepted benchmark of $\alpha = 0.70$ (Bainstein & Nunnally, 1994), indicating robust reliability. This process helped in identifying key dimensions within the dataset, providing a clearer understanding of the underlying factors influencing the sales performance and social selling strategies. For further details, refer to Table 2 below.

Table 2. Factor loading, Reliability test and Explained Variance

Constructs	1	2	3	4
Sales performance				
Contribution to your company's market share.	.91			
Selling high profit margin products.	.91			
Generating a high level of dollar sales.	.89			
Quickly generating sales of new company products.	.89			
Identifying and cultivating major accounts in your territory.	.75			
Exceeding sales targets.	.72			
Assisting your supervising manager in meeting his or her goals.	.71			
Social Selling- Insight				
I always social media to help me understand what my customers truly need		.84		
I always use social media to actively search for new sales opportunities		.82		
I systematically use social media to learn about the people or companies I want to sell to before reaching out		.75		
I leverage social media to identify people and companies that fit the ideal client profile		.73		
Social selling - Connection				
I leverage on social media to establish connections with various industry influencers.			.89	
I have a consistent dialogue with my connections to maintain my professional network.			.83	
When I meet people, I always try to create a connection with them in social media platforms, such as LinkedIn			.72	
I leverage relevant social media channels to gather a core audience of clients, industry peers, and prospects in order to lay a foundation of trust			.70	
Social Selling - Engagement				
I systematically share contents that demonstrates my expertise on some subject matter on social media				.85
I put a great deal of effort into sharing relevant, compelling, and timely content for my target audiences				.82
I engage potential customers with helpful content in social media to attain the position of a trusted advisor				.82
I actively share references, successful case histories, and experiences in social media to demonstrate how my firm can support customers' businesses				.73
Cronbach alpha	.90	.86	.84	.80
Total variance explained	36.84	17.95	7.83	6.27

Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated were tested using multiple regression analysis and the p-value was set at a 5% level ($p < 0.05$). In other words, we accept the alternate and reject the null when p is less than 0.05 and vice versa. Before testing the hypotheses, we tested for model fit and multi-collinearity as a prerequisite for multiple regression analysis. The ANOVA result showed that the overall model is a good fit ($F = 81.3, p < 0.001$). The

Variance Inflation Factor was all above the threshold of 3. Which suggests that the data is free from multi-collinearity problems. Also, the model summary result shows that the r-square is 65% and the adjusted r-square is 64%. This model explains less than 65% of the variance in the dependent variable. All the measures have a reliability score above 0.70. All the analysis was performed with the aid of the computer software, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 22.

In the first hypothesis, social selling insight generation was predicted to have a positive effect sales performance. The result found support for H1. Social selling insight generation has a positive and significant effect on sales performance ($\beta = .67$, $t = 6.53$, $p < 0.01$). In other words, listening to customers' social media conversations provides insight that can improve sales performance.

Hypothesis 2 predicted that social selling connection would have a positive effect on sales performance. The result showed a non-significant but positive effect of social selling connection on salesperson performance. Thus, the result does not support the H2. Therefore, we conclude that there is a non-significant effect of social selling connection on sales performance ($\beta = .15$, $t = 1.53$, $p < .13$).

Furthermore, we found support for hypothesis 3. The hypothesis predicted a positive effect of social selling engagement on sales performance. The p-value was below the 0.05 point. Therefore, we conclude that social selling engagement has a positive and significant effect on sales performance ($\beta = .60$, $t = 9.20$, $p < .01$). Finally, the result shows that social selling insight had the most effect on sales performance.

Table 5. Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	4.208	1.416		2.972	.004		
	Social Selling Insight	.674	.103	.454	6.528	.000	.546	1.830
	Social Selling Connection	.151	.099	.108	1.530	.128	.531	1.884
	Social selling Engagement	.601	.065	.491	9.203	.000	.929	1.077
	<i>F- Stat</i>	81.33				.000 ^a		
	<i>Adjusted R</i>	.65						
	<i>Adjusted R²</i>	.64						
a. Dependent Variable: Sales performance								

** significant
ns: not significant

Figure 2. Hypotheses result

Discussion

Social media offers numerous opportunities for businesses, with salespeople increasingly harnessing its potential to enhance performance and efficiency. This study investigates the impact of social media use, specifically social selling, on sales performance. The results indicate that both social selling insight and social selling engagement predict sales performance, while social selling connection exhibits a non-significant effect.

The positive impact of social selling insight on salesperson performance suggests that salespeople utilize the platform to comprehend customer needs, actively seek sales opportunities, conduct pre-outreach research on individuals or companies, and identify those aligning with the ideal client profile. This finding aligns with Cheng et al. (2023) and Terho et al. (2022), supporting the notion that social media aids buyer surveillance, guiding content creation and sales message preparation. Salespeople generate insight when they track conversations and brand mentions on LinkedIn, Facebook, or Twitter. Again, by joining online communities and participating in discussions and fora in their respective sector, salespeople gather relevant insights about customers that improves their sales outcome.

In contrast to existing studies and the second hypothesis, social selling connection does not significantly determine sales performance. Despite the main purpose of social media being to connect with people, the non-significant effect may be attributed to our respondents' predominant use of WhatsApp, followed by Facebook and LinkedIn. Previous research highlights LinkedIn's efficacy for sales-oriented connections (Terho et al., 2022; Mora Cortez et al., 2023). Additionally, the way salespeople communicate on these platforms, as suggested by Schendzielarz et al. (2022), influences the impact of social media adoption on performance.

The third hypothesis affirms a positive effect of social selling engagement on sales performance. This aligns with findings from Chaker et al. (2022), Terho et al. (2022), and Ancillai et al. (2019), emphasizing that social selling extends beyond sales-focused communication, engaging relevant actors with content tailored to their interests, goals, and problems. In summary, consistent with Frank and Dempark (2023), the use of social media in sales improves overall performance. Actively using social media to engage with customers, prospects, and stakeholders enhances salespersons' performance. Salespeople creatively leveraging social media to share relevant, compelling, and timely content demonstrate expert knowledge, contributing to improved sales. For instance, by sharing tips about products, educating customers, and telling stories salespeople engage customers, and through this engagement their sales performance improves.

Conclusion

Social selling significantly enhances sales performance by leveraging social media platforms. Salespeople utilizing these channels not only gain valuable insights into customer conversations but also understand their needs and interests, contributing to a performance boost. Moreover, social media serves as a scouting ground for identifying new sales opportunities and leads for potential prospects. In addition to these benefits, social selling provides salespeople with a unique platform for promoting products or services without a hard-selling approach. This involves sharing relevant content, posts, and helpful tips, fostering engagement with customers and various stakeholders, ultimately building trust. The engagement achieved through this approach plays a crucial role in elevating salespeople's overall performance. Furthermore, social media facilitates connections with other relevant actors and potential prospects. While the current study did not observe a significant effect in this regard, it acknowledges the importance of this aspect within the social selling model. Social selling acts as a catalyst for salespeople to establish connections with prospective customers, other relevant actors, and decision-makers in the industry. In summary, social selling, through its multifaceted approach, not only enhances sales performance but also establishes meaningful connections that contribute to the success of salespeople in engaging with their target audience.

Implications

To harness the potential of social selling for insight generation and improved sales performance, the findings from this study has some implication for practice:

First, sales organizations must initiate training programs for sales teams, focusing on adept usage of diverse social media platforms and understanding the subtleties of their operation. This training equips salespeople with the efficacy and confidence to leverage these tools effectively, gaining a competitive advantage and enhancing overall performance. This encompasses the creation of compelling profiles, development of engaging content, implementation of social media marketing strategies, and efficient reputation management. Sales organizations should provide relevant social media management tools to facilitate tracking keywords related to the company, brand, industry, and competition.

Second, Social selling serves as a valuable tool for salespeople to generate insights about customers, prospects, and key industry players. Sales teams should be equipped and encouraged to actively 'listen' to social conversations, identifying mentions of their brands, industry trends, or competitors. This information enables tailored solutions, addressing customer needs and fostering engagement based on unique preferences or pain points. Social media insights also contribute to understanding competitors' perceptions and strategies, allowing salespeople to craft a distinctive competitive positioning and adapt their selling efforts accordingly.

Finally, social selling significantly enhances performance by engaging a relevant audience. Sales organizations should proactively monitor conversations for engagement opportunities, identifying relevant discussions and trending topics. Effective engagement involves providing insights, solutions, and valuable information centered on the industry. Salespeople should be motivated to share educational and engaging content, including blog posts, videos, infographics, and GIFs. This positions them as authoritative figures in the industry, fostering credibility and trust.

Suggestions for Further Research

This study delved into the realm of social selling within B2B sectors, encompassing industries like FMCGs, services, beverages, and more. While the research covered a diverse range of industries, the sample size remained modest, limiting the confidence in generalizing the findings. To enhance the robustness of future studies, it is recommended to employ larger sample sizes spanning various sectors. Furthermore, extending the scope of investigation to include B2C salespersons and entrepreneurs could provide valuable insights into the diverse applications of social selling across different selling functions.

Considering that social media is a contemporary technology, particularly prevalent among Gen Z and Millennials, exploring how salespeople from different generational cohorts utilize social media for their selling functions would offer valuable perspectives. Additionally, examining the impact of social selling on various organizational outcomes, such as positive word-of-mouth intention, customer engagement, marketing, and innovation performance, adds depth to our understanding.

Considering the ever-expanding landscape of social media platforms, including the likes of TikTok, LinkedIn, Facebook, and others, it becomes crucial to unravel how salespeople leverage these platforms for various sales functions. This comprehensive exploration will contribute to a nuanced understanding of the evolving dynamics of social selling.

References

- Agnihotri, R., Kothandaraman, P., Kashyap, R. & Singh, R. (2012). Bringing “social” into sales: the impact of salespeople’s social media use on service behaviors and value creation. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 32(3), pp. 333-348.

- Ancillai, C., Terho, H., Cardinali, S., & Pascucci, F. (2019). Advancing social media driven sales research: Establishing conceptual foundations for B-to-B social selling. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 82, 293–308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2019.01.002>
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), 99–120. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639101700108>
- Chaker, N. N., Nowlin, E. L., Pivonka, M. T., Itani, O. S., & Agnihotri, R. (2022). Inside sales social media use and its strategic implications for salesperson-customer digital engagement and performance. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 100, 127–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2021.10.006>.
- Choudhury, M.M., & Harrigan, P., (2014). CRM to social CRM: the integration of new technologies into customer relationship management. *J. Strat. Market.* 22 (2), 149–176.
- Chawla, V., Lyngdoh, T., Guda, S., & Purani, K. (2020). Systematic review of determinants of sales performance: Verbeke et al. 's (2011) classification extended. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 35(8), 1359–1383. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-07-2019-0322>.
- Chatterjee, S., Chaudhuri, R., & Vrontis. D. (2022). AI and Digitalization in Relationship Management: Impact of Adopting AI-Embedded CRM System. *Journal of Business Research* 150, 437–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.06.033>.
- Cheng, Z., Plangger, K., Cai, F., Campbell, C. L., & Pitt, L. (2023). Charting value creation strategies B2B salespeople use throughout the sales process: Learning from social media influencers. *European Journal of Marketing*, 57(3), 718–744. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-11-2021-0922>.
- Dixon, S. J. (2023). Social media: global daily usage Q1 2023, by territory. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/270229/usage-duration-of-social-networks-by-country> (Accessed 22/10/2023).
- Eller, R., Alford, P., Kallmünzer, A., & Peters, M. (2020). Antecedents, consequences, and challenges of small and medium-sized enterprise digitalization. *Journal of Business Research*, 112, 119–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.03.004>.
- Euromonitor International (2024). Direct Selling in Nigera. <https://www.euromonitor.com/direct-selling-in-nigeria/report#> (accessed 20/5/2024)
- Franck, R., & Damperat, M. (2023). How social media use enhances salesperson performance. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 38(8), 1720–1737. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-02-2022-0082>

- Good, M. C., & Schwepker, C. H. (2022). Business-to-business salespeople and political skill: Relationship building, deviance, and performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 139, 32–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.09.035>
- Itani, O. S., Agnihotri, R., & Dingus, R. (2017). Social media use in B2b sales and its impact on competitive intelligence collection and adaptive selling: Examining the role of learning orientation as an enabler. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 66, 64–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2017.06.012>
- Itani, O. S., Badrinarayanan, V., & Rangarajan, D. (2023). The impact of business-to-business salespeople's social media use on value co-creation and cross/up-selling: The role of social capital. *European Journal of Marketing*, 57(3), 683–717. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-11-2021-0916>
- Jridi, K., Chaabouni, A. & Triki, A. (2019). Reconciliation of deterministic and knowledge management approaches for a better understanding of SFA's impact on salespersons' performance: very informal newsletter on library automation. *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems* 49 (3):353–71. doi: 10.1108/VJIKMS- 11-2018-0103.
- Minsky, L., & Quesenberry, K. A. (2016). How B2B sales can benefit from social selling. *Harvard Business Review*, 8,2–5.
- Mikalef, P., & Gupta, M. (2021). Artificial intelligence capability: Conceptualization, measurement calibration, and empirical study on its impact on organizational creativity and firm performance. *Information & Management*, 58(3), 103434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2021.103434>
- Mora Cortez, R., Johnston, W. J., & Ghosh Dastidar, A. (2023). Managing the content of LinkedIn posts: Influence on B2B customer engagement and sales? *Journal of Business Research*, 155, 113388. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.113388>
- Mostafa, R. B., & Kasamani, T. (2022). The Effect of Salespeople Skills on Selling Behaviors: The Moderating Role of Social Media. *Journal of Promotion Management*, 28(7), 961–993. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10496491.2022.2054900>
- Ogilvie, J., Agnihotri, R., Rapp, A., & Trainor, K. (2018). Social media technology use and salesperson performance: A two study examination of the role of salesperson behaviors, characteristics, and training. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 75, 55–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2018.03.007>
- Pervaje, A. (2011). Resource-Based View of Social Media as a Source of Sustained Competitive Advantage [M.Sc]. Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Schendzielarz, D., Alavi, S., & Guba, J. H. (2022). The impact of salespeople's social media adoption on customer acquisition performance – a contextual perspective. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 42(2), 139–157. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08853134.2022.2033624>

- Schmitt, L., Casenave, E., & Pallud, J. (2021). Salespeople's work toward the institutionalization of social selling practices. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 96, 183–196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2021.05.008>
- Terho, H., Giovannetti, M., & Cardinali, S. (2022). Measuring B2B social selling: Key activities, antecedents and performance outcomes. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 101, 208–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2021.12.016>
- Trainor, K. J. (2012). Relating Social Media Technologies to Performance: A Capabilities-Based Perspective, *Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management*, 32 (3), 317-331.
- Vander Schee, B., Peltier, J. W., & Dahl, A. J. (2020). Antecedent consumer factors, consequential branding outcomes and measures of online consumer engagement: Current research and future directions. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 14(2), 239–268. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIM-01-2020-0010>.
- Zhou, J., & Charoensukmongkol, P. (2021). The effect of social media use on customer qualification skills and adaptive selling behaviors of export salespeople in China. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 15(2), 278–300. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABS-12-2019-0377>.

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2024 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Dike, V., Nwaizugbo, I., & Ojiaku, O. (2024). Effect of Social Selling on Salespersons' Performance: Evidence from B2B Salespersons in an Emerging Country Context. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 11(9), 1268-1284.</p> <p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13764990</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_204041.html</p>	